

Kinetics and mechanism of electron-transfer reactions : Oxidation of pyruvic acid by peroxomonosulphuric acid in acid aqueous medium

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Abstract : Kinetics of oxidation of pyruvic acid (Pyr) by peroxomonosulphate (PMS) has been studied in aqueous acidic medium. The observed stoichiometry corresponds to the reaction as represented by the eq. (i),

The reaction is simple second order and the rate law given by the eq. (ii) was derived from the proposed mechanism.

$$-\frac{d[\text{PMS}]}{dt} = \frac{kK_a[\text{PMS}][\text{Pyr}]}{[\text{H}^+] + K_a} \quad (\text{ii})$$

Keywords : Electron transfer reactions, pyruvic acid, permonosulphuric acid.

Potassium peroxomonosulphate (Oxone) is a triple salt of the composition $2\text{KHSO}_5 \cdot \text{KHSO}_4 \cdot \text{K}_2\text{SO}_4$. However, it is difficult to prepare simple peroxomonosulphate salt and is still more difficult to purify the salt free from KHSO_4 and K_2SO_4 salts which are present to the extent of $\sim 4\%$. Peroxomonosulphate ion is a monosubstituted derivative of H_2O_2 i.e. HOOSO_3^- but this peroxy salt is kinetically more reactive than H_2O_2 despite the fact that the oxidation potential of the couple $E_{\text{HSO}_5^-/\text{HSO}_4^-}$ (1.82 V) is not much different from that of the couple $E_{\text{H}_2\text{O}_2/\text{O}_2}$ (1.776 V). Moreover, spontaneous decomposition of H_2O_2 in water further justifies that the HSO_5^- is more stable than H_2O_2 . However, HSO_5^- decomposes readily only when pH is equal to $\text{p}K_2^1$.

HSO_5^- is considered to be a potential oxidant in reactions where H_2O_2 is normally encountered as a mild oxidant. α -Keto acids are known to be biologically important class of carboxylic acids. A large number of kinetic studies of the oxidation of these acids both by metal and non-metal ion oxidants has been reported both in acid and alkaline media². In fact, these were certain studies that prompted us to undertake the kinetics of the title reaction from the following view-points :

First the Caro's acid is a strong acid with $\text{p}K_1 < 0$. It is slowly hydrolysed to H_2O_2 in strong acid medium¹. Secondly the heterolytic scission of the (-O-O-) peroxide bond has been suggested to be the rate-limiting step for the oxidation of most of the nucleophiles, it will be tempt-

ing to probe whether or not the similar trend is observed in the title reaction.

Experimental

A triple salt ($2\text{KHSO}_5 \cdot \text{KHSO}_4 \cdot \text{K}_2\text{SO}_4$) known by its trade name 'Oxone' (Aldrich) was employed for peroxomonosulphate. The solution of the peracid was prepared by dissolving its potassium salt in doubly distilled water, and was standardised both iodometrically as well as cerimetrically. Impurity of either KHSO_4 , K_2SO_4 or both was found to the extent of $\sim 4\%$. The presence of KHSO_4 or K_2SO_4 or both in the solution to this extent did not interfere with the kinetics of the title reaction. Further the presence of H_2O_2 reported owing to the salt hydrolysis was negated by testing peracid solution with dilute solution of permanganate. All other reagents were either of analytical or reagent grade and were employed as supplied.

Reaction mixtures containing all of its ingredients and peroxomonosulphate were respectively taken in glass stoppered Erlenmeyer flasks suspended in a water bath thermostated at $\pm 0.1^\circ\text{C}$ unless specified otherwise. Peroxomonosulphate of the desired concentration was taken out and then discharged into the reaction mixture, the time of initiation of the reaction was recorded when half of the contents from the pipette were released. An aliquot (5 cm^3) of the reaction mixture was withdrawn periodically to assay the remaining peroxomonosulphate

(heretofore written as PMS) iodometrically. However, results were not reproducible with batch changing samples.

Initial rates (k_i mol dm⁻³ s⁻¹) were computed employing plane mirror method. Pseudo-first order plots were made wherever reaction conditions permitted. Second order plots were also made for comparable concentrations of the reactants. The results in triplicate were reproducible to within ±6%.

Stoichiometry : The stoichiometry of the reaction was determined by allowing the reaction mixtures ([PMS] > [Pyr]) in a thermostated water bath at (30 ± 0.1) °C for ca. 5 h. The excess concentration of peroxomonosulphate on completion of the reaction was measured iodometrically.

The stoichiometry conform to the reaction as represented by the eq. (1).

Such a stoichiometry was further confirmed kinetically. Certain reactions of peroxomonosulphate and pyruvic acid in stoichiometric concentrations [mol dm⁻³] at pH 4.06 were carried out in a thermostated water bath maintained at (30 ± 0.1) °C. The rate constants were evaluated in usual manner from the plots of 1/[PMS]_t versus time (Table 1) and agreed well with k_2 calculated by other methods (Table 2).

Table 1. Second order rate constant (k_2) in reactions of peroxomonosulphate and pyruvic acid in stoichiometric concentrations

pH 4.06, temp. 30 °C		
10 ³ [PMS] (mol dm ⁻³)	10 ³ [Pyr] (mol dm ⁻³)	10 ³ k_2 (dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)
2.0	2.0	8.8
4.0	4.0	8.3
6.0	6.0	8.7
8.0	8.0	8.6
10.0	10.0	8.8
20.0	20.0	8.8

Results

Peroxomonosulphate dependence : The concentration of peroxomonosulphate was varied from 1.0 × 10⁻³ to 1.0 × 10⁻² mol dm⁻³ at two but fixed concentrations of pyruvic acid to be 1.0 × 10⁻² and 2.0 × 10⁻² mol dm⁻³ respectively, pH 4.06 and 30 °C (pH was maintained by employing acetic acid and sodium acetate buffers). Initial rates (k_i) were calculated and a plot of initial rate (k_i)

versus [PMS] yielded a straight line passing through the origin indicating first order dependence with respect to peracid. Further the concentration of peroxomonosulphate was also varied in the range 1.0 × 10⁻³ to 5.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³ and 1 × 10⁻³ to 1.0 × 10⁻² mol dm⁻³ at two different but constant concentrations of pyruvic acid to be 5.0 × 10⁻² and 10 × 10⁻² mol dm⁻³ respectively. Pseudo-first order plots were made wherever reaction conditions permitted and pseudo-first order rate constants (k' , s⁻¹) were found to be independent of the initial concentrations of the peracid further confirming first order dependence with respect to the latter. Second order plots were also constructed and the second order rate constants derived from these plots were found in agreement with those calculated from initial rates (k' , mol dm⁻³ s⁻¹) and pseudo-first order rate constants (k' , s⁻¹) (Table 2).

Table 2. Initial rates (k_i , mol dm⁻³ s⁻¹), pseudo-first order (k' , s⁻¹) and second order rate constants (k_2 , dm³ mol⁻¹ s⁻¹) in the reaction of peroxomonosulphate and pyruvic acid

pH 4.06, temp. 30 °C				
10 ³ [PMS] (mol dm ⁻³)	10 ³ [Pyr] (mol dm ⁻³)	10 ⁷ (k_i) (mol dm ⁻³ s ⁻¹)	10 ⁴ k' (s ⁻¹)	10 ² k_2 (dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)
2.0	10.0	16.6	-	8.8 (8.3) -
5.0	10.0	42.0	-	8.0 (8.4) -
10.0	10.0	86.6	-	- (8.7) -
1.0	20.0	-	15.8	- - -
5.0	10.0	77.7	-	(7.9) - -
1.0	50.0	-	38.3	- - 7.8
1.0	100.0	-	79.7	- - 8.0
2.0	2.0	3.33	-	- (8.3) -
2.0	5.0	8.33	-	8.3 (8.3) -
2.0	10.0	42.0	-	8.2 (8.4) -
5.0	15.0	60.0	-	8.1 (8.0) -
5.0	45.0	175.0	-	8.1 (8.2) -
5.0	50.0	-	41.0	- (8.2) 8.1
5.0	100.0	-	80.6	- (8.1) 8.0

k_2 in parentheses were calculated from second order plots.

Pyruvic acid dependence : The concentration of pyruvic acid was varied from 2.0 × 10⁻³ to 10 × 10⁻² mol dm⁻³ at fixed concentrations of peroxomonosulphate viz. 2.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³ and pH 4.06 at 30 °C. Initial rates were calculated and plot of initial rate against [Pyr] yielded a straight line passing through the origin confirming first order dependence with respect to pyruvic acid. The empirical rate eq. (2) accounts for the rate dependence on the concentrations of peroxomonosulphate and pyruvic acid respectively.

$$-\frac{d[\text{PMS}]}{dt} = A[\text{PMS}][\text{Pyr}] \quad (2)$$

where A is an empirical constant. Second order rate constants are compiled in Table 2.

pH dependence : The effect of pH on the rate was studied by varying pH in a limited range from 3.19 to 4.48 employing acetate buffers at fixed concentrations of other reaction ingredients viz. $[\text{PMS}] = 2.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{Pyr}] = 2.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ at constant ionic strength to be 1.0 mol dm^{-3} (ionic strength (I) was adjusted by employing lithium perchlorate). The rate initially does not show any pH dependence but certainly exhibits rising trend in rate with increasing pH. The empirical rate eq. (3) accounts for such a pH dependence.

$$-\frac{d[\text{PMS}]}{dt} = \frac{A[\text{PMS}][\text{Pyr}]}{B + [\text{H}^+]} \quad (3)$$

where B is also an empirical constant.

Effect of ionic strength (I) : The effect of ionic strength (I) was studied by employing lithium perchlorate at fixed concentrations of other reaction components viz. $[\text{PMS}] = 2.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{Pyr}] = 2.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and pH 4.06 at 30 °C. The rate increases with increasing ionic strength (Fig. 1).

The effect of *t*-butyl alcohol and benzene respectively was studied on the rate of the reaction. However, no effect was observed conforming to the fact that neither SO_4^- nor OH^- radicals participated in the reaction. The

Fig. 1. Effect of ionic strength : $[\text{PMS}] = 2.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{CH}_3\text{COCOONa}] = 1.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, pH = 4.06, 30 °C.

participation of free radicals was further tested by adding acrylic acid monomer in the reaction mixture. No white turbidity or precipitate was observed even after an hour of the reaction. This also eliminates the participation of free radicals in the reaction.

Discussion

Peroxomonosulphate decomposes rapidly in strong acid medium and the mechanism of decomposition involves an interaction between HSO_5^- and SO_5^{2-} . Since pH employed in the reaction is far less than $\text{p}K_2$, the possibility for the peracid to exist in SO_5^{2-} form is ruled out. It is, therefore, reasonable to assume HSO_5^- to be the reactive form of peroxomonosulphuric acid. Moreover, the rate dependence on pH though not of marked influence can not be correlated to the peracid. If $\text{p}K$ of the pyruvic acid and pH of the reaction mixture are taken into account, the dissociated form of keto acid appears to be the reactive species.

Thus considering HSO_5^- and Pyr^- to be the reactive forms of peroxomonosulphuric acid and pyruvic acid respectively, the following reaction mechanism can be envisaged to account for the experimental observations.

The bimolecular interaction between HSO_5^- and Pyr^- is further supported by the effect of ionic strength the rate as the latter increases with increasing ionic strength. Since the rate increases due to interaction of anionic species, the second order rate constant should obey Bronsted-Bjerrum Christiansen relationship¹⁵ (eq. (6)),

$$\log k_2 = \log k_0 + \frac{2Z_A Z_B \alpha \sqrt{I}}{1 + \beta \sqrt{I}} \quad (6)$$

The eq. (6) reduce to eq. (7) at 298 K employing $\alpha = 0.509$ and $\beta = 1$.

$$\log k_2 = \log k_0 + 1.02Z_A Z_B \frac{\sqrt{I}}{1 + \sqrt{I}} \quad (7)$$

A plot of $\log k_2$ versus $\left(\frac{\sqrt{I}}{1 + \sqrt{I}}\right)$ at lower ionic strength

was made from eq. (7) that yielded a straight line with non-zero intercept (Fig. 1), the slope of the line observed to be ~ 0.9 is very close to 1.0 and agrees with the

charges on the oxidant and substrate in the rate determining step of the reaction mechanism.

Thus the loss of peracid leads to the rate law (8) or (9).

$$-\frac{d[\text{PMS}]}{dt} = \frac{kK_d [\text{HSO}_5^-] [\text{Pyr}]}{[\text{H}^+] + K_d} \quad (8)$$

where $[\text{HSO}_5^-]$ and $[\text{Pyr}]$ are the gross analytical concentrations of peracid and pyruvic acid respectively.

or

$$k_2 = kK_d/([\text{H}^+] + K_d) \quad (9)$$

where k_2 is an observed second order rate constant (Table 1).

The reaction appears to occur via an activated state $[\text{HSO}_5^- \text{--} \text{Pyr}^-]$ which undergoes redox decomposition yielding end-products. Since, such an adduct formation is established neither kinetically nor spectrophotometrically, it is still a path of choice that requires lesser energy.

The reciprocal of eq. (7) on re-arrangement yields eq. (8)

$$\frac{1}{k_2} = \frac{[\text{H}^+]}{kK_d} + \frac{1}{k} \quad (8)$$

A plot of $1/k_2$ versus $[\text{H}^+]$ was made from eq. (8) (Fig. 2) that yielded a straight line with non-zero intercept, k was calculated from the intercept to be $10.6 \pm 0.2 \text{ dm}^3$

Fig. 2. Plot of $[k_2]^{-1}$ versus $[\text{H}^+]$: $[\text{PMS}] = 2.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{Pyr}] = 2.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $I = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and 30°C .

$\text{mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and K_d from the ratio of intercept and slope to be $(2.9 \pm 0.1) \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ at $I = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and 30°C . The value of k_d is in excellent agreement with the value reported earlier.

The uncatalyzed oxidation of α -keto acids is reported to occur through the rupture of C-C bond. Thus the possible mode of electron transfer can be envisaged by considering the following reaction Scheme 1 in a converted manner.

Scheme 1

The free radical mechanism was not considered owing to the facts that (I) benzene is considered to be a good scavenger of sulphate free radical ions but does not affect the rate. Secondly, the acrylic acid is not polymerized in the reaction mixture. The rate is also not affected by *t*-butyl alcohol—a scavenger of OH free radicals and this also rules out any involvement of OH radicals in the reaction. If these experimental observations are taken into account, free radical involvement is ruled out. Since $E_{\text{HSO}_5^-/\text{HSO}_4^-}$ is significantly less than that of $E_{\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}/\text{SO}_4^{2-}}$ redox couple, the reactions of the former are significantly faster than those of peroxodisulphate despite the presence of peroxide bonds. It appears that homolytic session as is considered to be the reason of the formation of free radicals in all probability does not take place in case of peroxomonosulphate.

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